

Evaluation of Moroccan Milk Quality in Dairy Herds: Inter-Relationship between Chemical, Physical and Hygienic Criteria

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ABSTRACT_ This is the first study interested of inter-relationships between different aspects of dairy milk quality that remains not well documented in Morocco. The principal objective of this study was to assess the overall milk quality and inter-relationship between chemical, physical and hygienic criteria in Moroccan dairy herds. All milk samples were analyzed for microbiological, antibiotics residues, somatic cells, chemical and physical parameters. In general, the findings obtained from this study show a variability average in the physicochemical and microbiological quality of raw milk between different studied regions. Several physicochemical parameters were associated. For example, solids no fat, fat content, protein content, brix and density were consistently associated. Thus, one of these parameters can be used as a chemical indicator of milk quality. In addition, the *S. aureus*, total and fecal coliforms were consistently associated with total aerobic flora. Therefore, the last criteria can be used only as a hygienic indicator of milk quality. All milk samples were negatives for the major pathogenic bacteria and also for the detection of antibiotics residues. The somatic milk cells count remains generally in concordance with what announced by standards. The research of these last three parameters could practice as indicators of mammary gland infection. In conclusion, milk producers have at hand rapid, easy and economical tools for evaluating the global quality of milk.

Key words_ Morocco, Inter-relationship, Somatic cells, microbiological analysis, physicochemical analysis.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In Morocco, the dairy production of cattle enjoys generally a very special position in agricultural development plans [1]. Certainly, this vital sector assumes a fundamental nutritional role of supplying animal proteins to an urban population in full demographic growing and whose eating habits evolve towards more quality [2]. Hence, to ensure self-sufficiency in milk and its derivatives, Morocco has intensively and continuously encouraged milk production since the seventies of the last century [3], to face demographical grow and its consequences [4,5]. In 1975, Morocco has launched the first important dairy plan (setting up of a production, processing and collection structure) [6]. As consequence, this sector has known a significant growing from 521.6 million liters in 1975 to 2.6 billion liters in 2015 [6]. The evolution of this sector is in agreement with the desired objectives of the new Moroccan agricultural strategy (the Moroccan Green Plan) for food self-sufficiency in horizon of 2020. It concerned seven basic alimentary products indispensable to the Moroccan diet where milk is considered as an important one [7]. For this reason, Morocco has re-launched the program-contract signed by the public authorities and sector in 2015, which therefore provides for the kingdom to move from a collection of 2.4 billion liters in 2013 to 4 billion in 2020, an increase of 1.55 billion liters compared to 2015 and a turnover of 23 billion dirhams [6]. This 2015-2020 national program-contract hops also to increase the average annual per capita consumption to 90 liters [6]. In addition, dairy farming has significant social and economic roles in creating jobs and wealth in the many farms holding cows [8]. Nevertheless, this challenge regarding milk quantities to produce poses the problem of the quality of raw milk produced. Hence, if the produced quantities of milk are today in general satisfactory because of the remarkable efforts that deploy by Kingdom in this regards (encouraging milk production principally cow milk) many problems linked to the quality standards which are very hard to meet [4,9-13] still exist which constitutes a challenge for the agro-alimentary sector especially dairy industry in the kingdom [14,15]. Among these problems, we cited two major factors. The first one is directly related with the heterogeneity of raw milk's compositions, influenced by various factors such as the breeding, geographical area, climate conditions and nutritional factors [11,14-16] whereas the second one is looked in difficulty to respect hygienic procedures conducting to an important microbial load touching the hygienic quality

and representing in this a serious danger for human health [17]. In raw milk, the search of the pathogenic germs constitutes an imperative tool to assess this quality especially for raw milk destined to be processed. The bacteria enumeration reflecting the hygienic state of the milk such as Total Aerobic Mesophilic Flora, Fecal and Total Coliforms stays the most commonly utilized method in dairy herds with the search for pathogenic germs such as *Salmonella* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and Anaerobic Sulfite-reducing Bacteria [14,15]. Several of these microorganisms have been recognized as etiological agents of bovine mastitis [18]. Mastitis consists of an inflammation of the mammary gland, usually developed in response to an intramammary bacterial infection [19-21]. The glands epithelial cells are normally shed and get renewed; however, during infection the numbers increase according to Sharma *et al.* [22]. Instead, the white blood cells serve as a defense mechanism to fight infection and assist in the repair of damaged tissue [22,23]. Somatic cells are mainly defined as milk-secreting epithelial cells that have been shed from the lining of the gland and white blood cells (leukocytes) that have entered the mammary gland in response to injury or infection [24]. In veterinary medicine, antimicrobial agents play an important role in the therapy of bacterial infections [25]. In herds, ~80% of antimicrobials are reported for the treatment of bovine mastitis [26], as antibiotic therapy remains the primary choice for mastitis control in lactating and dry cows [27].

To our knowledge, this is the first study interested of inter-relationships between different aspects of dairy milk quality that remains not well documented in Morocco. The main objective of the present study was to evaluate the physicochemical and hygienic quality of raw cow milk produced in Fkih-ben-saleh, Souk-sebt, Oued-zem and Khouribga regions on the one hand and to evaluate the inter-relationship between chemical, physical and hygienic criteria on the one other hand. In general, the idea of this study was also to offer to industries and dairy producers some practical analytical criteria to evaluate global milk quality, and in particular hygienic quality.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling regions

This study was carried out in different irrigated perimeters of the Fkih-ben-salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions, located in the north-central of Morocco (Figure 1). Almost of these regions are located in Plain of Tadla and have

been selected for their potential milk production. The plain parts are well developed and the agriculture is largely based on irrigation methods and several farms have developed their activities inside them and there is large milk production from cows and goats [14,15].

Fig 1. Presentation of sampling regions.

Climate conditions

The Moroccan climate changes according to the season and the region. The coast has a moderate Mediterranean climate on the coast and the trade winds. Interior regions have a warmer and drier climate, the continental climate. It is very difficult, if not impossible, to predict what the weather will be like at a certain time in a very precise place. Overall, the climate of Tadla plain is well-known by arid to semi-arid with a dry season from April to October and it is also characterized by a rainy season from November to March [28]. The annual cumulative rainfall varies from 149 to 397 mm between 2000 and 2013 while the seasonal variations of temperature are significant with a maximum in August of 46°C, a minimum in January of -6°C and an annual average of 20°C [29].

Sampling preparation

In the year 2023, a total of more than 400 samples raw milk was collected into sterile bottles (about 1000ml) for physicochemical analysis and in the sterile flasks for microbiological analysis from seventeen farms randomly selected in these regions

already described and transported immediately in thermos-cool boxes (at 4°C). All the collection samples were taking at the morning and afternoon milking and all physico-chemical parameters and also hygienic criteria were directly determined on the day or night of sampling.

Physicochemical analysis

In general, after sample collection, the temperature of the milk is directly measured in place with a thermometer. Once raw milk samples arrived at laboratory in an insulated cooler containing ice cubes (thermos-cool boxes (at 4°C)), the physical, chemical and hygienic parameters are measured and analyzed; respectively. Thus, the pH is immediately measured using an Orion Reseach pH-meter after calibration at pH 7.02 and 4.00 by soaking in a small volume of milk taken from a beaker [30] while titratable acidity is measured by titration with 1N NaOH in the presence of phenolphthalein and acidity of milk was expressed in degrees Doronic (°D) which is equivalent to a grade of 0.1g of lactic acid/L of milk [31]; the milk density is determined using a thermolactodensimeter. It is reduced to 20°C by the following formula: corrected density = density read +0.2 (milk temperature -20°C).

When the chemical criteria is considered, the fat content is firstly determined by the acid-butyrometric method of Gerber [32], which consists of an attack of milk with sulfuric acid and separation by centrifugation in the presence of isoamyl alcohol of the released fat [33,34] while the determination of the levels of proteins, fat, total solids, solids-non-fat is carried out using the milkoscan™ minor apparatus calibrated to official methods to determine the protein level (Gjeldal method), fat content (Gerber method) and total solids (desiccation method). The procedure is as follows: Select the measurement program then place a sample under the pipette and finally press start. The results are displayed directly on the screen or printed out; the results are expressed g/100g.

Microbiological analysis

The raw milk samples designated to microbiological analysis were taken in sterile flasks and transported immediately using an insulated cooler containing ice cubes at -18°C (thermos-cool boxes (at 4°C)) and in the dark to ensure permanent samples at a temperature between 0 and 4°C to block the multiplication of bacteria already present in the milk according to the rules of sampling proposed by the milk

committee to the laboratory for microbiological analyzes. To evaluate the hygienic quality of raw milk and the danger that can be presented by the presence of certain bacteria that are considered occasional visitors of raw milk. Dilutions of milk samples studied was performed in peptone water and varied from 10^{-1} to 10^{-7} . The isolation and enumeration of bacteria reflecting hygienic degree such as total aerobic flora, total coliforms, fecal coliforms and germs such as anaerobic sulphite-reducing bacteria, *S. aureus*, were carried out according international standards [35].

Bacteria enumeration

The non-selective culture medium Plate Count Agar (PCA) was used for counting of total aerobic flora (the incubation conditions were 72h at 30°C). Moreover, the Desoxycholate Lactose Agar (DL, Oxoid, England), a selective medium for the detection of enterobacteriaceae was used for enumeration of coliforms (the incubation was operated during 48h at 30°C for total coliforms and 44°C for fecal coliforms). For the *Salmonella* estimation, the Rappaport-Vassiliadis broth was utilized (24h at 42°C) and Hektoen medium (24h at 30°C) whereas the confirmation of identification of suspect colonies was made by the assistance of API20 E kit (BiomÃ©rieux, France). The detection of *L. monocytogenes* was performed by using broth Frazer (24h at 37°C) while the confirmation of suspect colonies was performed by the use of chromogenic medium with the API Listeria. Concerning the estimation of *S. aureus*, the incubation of diluted milk samples was made in Baird Parker media at 37°C during 48h [14,15]. Finally, the sulphite-reducing *clostridia* are counted on the Reinforced Clostridium Agar culture medium in tubes to favor the anaerobic conditions, with a heat treatment for 10 min at 80°C to activate the spores of Clostridia: they can persist in latent form in the milk, sprout as soon as conditions are favorable and secrete toxic substances. The tubes are incubated for 48 h at 37°C. Only black colonies are counted [30].

Data analysis

The data were regrouped and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 21 software. For quantitative variables, we used the t-test, which is the most common method for evaluating differences between the means of two groups. In the case of qualitative variables, we used the Chi-square test of independence. The level of significance was set to be < 0.05 .

III. RESULTS

The essential of results of the physicochemical, microbiological, somatic milk cell counts and chemical antibiotics residues analysis of raw cow's milk produced in different studied regions are presented in table 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Table 1. Physicochemical analysis average of raw milk obtained from Fkih-ben-saleh, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions.

Studied regions Types		Fkih-ben-saleh	Khouribga	Oued-zem	Souk-sebt
Physicochemical analyses (g/100ml)	FC	3.576	3.288	3.558	3.521
	PC	3.208	3.064	3.104	3.035
	TS	11.91	11.395	11.552	11.547
	SNF	9.043	8.761	8.675	8.706
	Ac	14.4	14.5	14.3	14
	Bx	10	09	09	9
	Ds	1.0320	1.0300	1.0301	1.0306
	pH	6.78	6.75	6.77	6.77
	T°	07	6.9	7.7	08
	TA	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative

“FC”: fat content, “PC”: protein content, “TS”: total solids, “SNF”: solids no fat “Ac”: acidity, “Bx”: brix, “Ds”: density, “T°”: temperature, “AT”: alcohol test.

The findings obtained from this study show a variability average in the nutritional quality and hygienic criteria of raw milk between different studied regions. In this regards, the milk fat content average obtained, in Fkih-ben-salh, Oued-zem, Souk-sebt and Khouribga regions, was 3.576, 3.558, 3.521 and 3.288 g/l, respectively. Moreover, the average values recorded of milk protein content was respectively about 3.208, 3.104, 3.035 and 3.064 g/l whereas the total solids were around 11.91, 11.552, 11.547 and 11.395 g/l, respectively; and an average of 9.043, 8.675, 8.706 and 8.761 g/l was respectively unregistered for solids no fat. Finally, the brix average rate oscillated between 09 to 10% for all studied regions (Table 1).

Concerning physical criteria, the result obtained of milk acidity collected from Fkih-ben-salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions was 14.4, 14.5, 14 and 14.3 D°, respectively. Moreover, the ionic acidity is oscillated from 6.75 to 6.78. The measurement of milk density in these regions ranged generally from 1.0300 to 1.0320 while temperature of all samples collected from bulk milk was in order 07 to 08 °C. All milk samples tested for alcohol testing were normal at 74% (Table 1).

Table 2. Microbiological analysis average of raw milk obtained from Fkih-ben-saleh, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions.

Types Studied Regions	Microbiological analysis (UFC/ml)										
	TC		FC		TAF		Pso	<i>S.ars</i>	<i>Salm.</i>	<i>Clsm.</i>	<i>Lis.</i>
	10 ⁻³	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻³	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁶	10 ⁻⁶	1 ml	-	-	-
Fkih-ben-salh	81.33	32.22	44.88	22.33	51.22	9.55	2.77	42	00.00	00.00	00.00
Khouribga	104.66	31.44	57.00	23.33	109.11	17.44	4.77	560	00.00	00.00	00.00
Souk-sebt	300.00	81.00	300.00	115.22	109.33	18.44	16.77	320	00.00	00.00	00.00
Oued-zem	166.40	38.70	147.10	26.88	140.11	24.00	13.66	800	00.00	00.00	00.00

TC, Total Coliforms; FC, Feecal Coliforms; TAF, Total Aerobic Flora; Pso, *Pseudomonas spp.*; *S.ars*, *Staphylococcus aureus*; *Salm.*, *Salmonella spp.*; *Clsm.*, *Clostridium*; *Lis.*, *Listeria monocytogenese*.

The analysis of the microbiological findings obtained for all the regions investigated in this study indicated that the great majority of milk caw samples studied were contaminated but at diverse levels. Indeed, the enumeration of fecal and total coliforms in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions, showed average values of 2.2×10^5 , 2.3×10^5 , 1.1×10^5 and 2.6×10^6 UFC/ml and 3.2×10^5 , 3.1×10^5 , 8.1×10^5 and 3.8×10^5 UFC/ml, respectively. When the *Pseudomonas spp.* enumeration was considered, the loads are in the range of 2.7×10^6 , 4.7×10^6 , 1.6×10^7 and 1.3×10^7 UFC/ml, in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions, respectively. In addition, the level of total aerobic flora showed the following values: 9.5×10^6 , 1.7×10^7 , 1.8×10^7 and 2.4×10^7 UFC/ml. Regarding the remaining pathogenic group bacteria analyzed in this study such as *S. aureus*, *Salmonella spp.*, *L. monocytogenes*, *Clostridium* we noticed their absence in all tested samples and in all studied regions (Table 2).

Table 3. Average of Somatic milk cell counts (cells/ml) obtained in Fkih-ben-salh, Khouribga, Oued-zem and Souk-sebt regions.

Studied regions Type	Fkih-ben-saleh	Khouribga	Oued-zem	Souk-sebt
SMCC (cells/ml)	344 400	284 200	323 900	331 800

SMCC: Somatic milkcell counts

The average values observed of SMCC in this study are 344 400, 284 200, 323 900 and 331 800 cells/ml in Fkih ben salh, Khouribga, Oued-zem and Souk-sebt regions, respectively (Table 3).

Table 4. Research of chemical antibiotics residues in all studied samples obtained from Fkih-ben-salh, Khouribga, Oued-zem and Souk-sebt regions.

Studied samples Type	Fkih-ben-saleh	Khouribga	Oued-zem	Souk-sebt
Delvotest method	100% Negative	100%Negative	100%Negative	100%Negative

All milk samples tested for the detection of chemical residues of the antibiotics were negatives (Table 4).

IV. DISCUSSION

Worldly, it is known that the rational feeding of dairy cows has generally a notable influence on both the quality and quantitative production of milk for industrial uses. According to Bérard *et al.* [36], the value or industrial quality of milk can be expressed by all the properties and physicochemical, biological and organoleptic characteristics necessary for ensure the production of high value dairy products commercial. In this study, the results obtained from different regions studied, showed the existence of different individual values with regard to chemical and physical criteria, depending on the region studied. Concerning the chemical findings found, the milk fat content average was oscillated between 3,2 and 3,5 g/l. In addition, the average values of milk protein content observed in these regions are ranged from 3.0 to 3,2 g/l whereas for the total solids they are between 113.9 and 119.1 g/l and between 87.0 and 90.4 g/l was unregistered for solids no fat. Finally, the brix rate oscillated between 09 to 10% for all investigated regions. These findings are associated mostly to various major factors like the extensive utilization of concentrate type of feeding given to cows on the one hand [37,38] and the farming nature practiced in these regions on the one other hand [10,11]. The fat finding found is situated over the limit range advanced by AFNOR for fat standard (28.5 to 32.5 g/l) [33]. This is of high economic importance for producers that are reattributed according principally to this criterion. This also reflects the efforts made by these producers to have highly standard raw milk by adopting good breeding practices particularly relative to nutritional aspect. According to Srairi *et al.* [1], dairy industries in Morocco apply penalties on quality under this threshold. The comparison of our results obtained in this study with those previously described by

Bassbassi *et al.* [5] from February to April in some farms and cooperatives in regions of Fkih-ben-salh, Kssiba and Kalaa especially for solids no-fat, protein and fat contents remain superior that what we found her particularly in farms case from Fkih-ben-salh: (fat: 41.05 g/kg, protein: 33.78 g/kg and solids no-fat: 96.81 g/kg), Kssiba: (fat: 41.16 g/kg, protein: 33.02 g/kg and solids no-fat: 96.67 g/kg) and from Kalaa: (fat: 38.28 g/kg, protein: 32.94 g/kg and solids no-fat: 95.36 g/kg). This important difference revealed a variability of nutritional milk quality between all considered regions in this study. This variation could be associated to the geographical difference that leads to the variation of climatic conditions and the ways to feed livestock and is also related to breeding conditions followed by the farmers in each region. In relation to our previous study, the heterogeneity of raw milk's compositions remains also influenced by the breeding, geographical zone, nutritional factors and climate conditions [14,15]. Additionally to nutritional supply, the climate is known to be an important factor that has an influence on the difference between the composition of the milk fat content in addition to the dry milk extracts. For example, Gonzalo *et al.* [39] reported that the water content of milk decreases in cold season and therefore its dry matter increases. Of note, the results given in this study are the average of measurements made a period of the year extended from January to June which could not reflect seasonal variations.

In Morocco, our findings obtained for fat content in the investigated regions remained higher than previous contents described by Labioui *et al.* [30] in Mnasra region (31.5 g/l) and lesser than value observed for total solids in this region (117.5 g/l). Moreover, our findings for protein content showed generally similar levels in comparison with those reported in Rabat-Sale region (a minimum of 30.8 g/kg and a maximum of 32.7 g/kg) whereas the fat level in this region stayed also in most cases higher than what has been shown in our study [1]. This could be related with a food system based on concentrates using more forage in the energy balance in the farms considered in Rabat-Sale region [1]. In general, the importance of the food type indicated to dairy cows must be taken into concern; for example, during drought periods, milk producers try to find choices to maize silage, principally in dry conditions. So, the cereal-legume bi-crop silage, sorghum or alfalfas represent interesting solutions. The sorghums use instead of maize silage have been allowed to decreased daily milk when sorghum silage was over 65% of the forages and the fat content have been also increased (2.6 to 4.4 g/kg) according to Rouille *et al.* [40].

The physical parameters are also measured in order to assess milk quality [41]. The measurement of milk density in these regions was between 1.0310 and 1.0318. According to Barboza and Miranda [42], the normal milk density was ranged from 1.030 to 1.035. When the values of the densities are below 1.030, milk samples are wetted causing by consequent a decrease in their densities. Moreover, the measurement of acidity degree determines technological suitability and indicates freshness of milk [43,44]. The acidity obtained of milk collected from the different studied regions was between 14 and 14.5 D°. In general, these findings were situated in the values reported by AFNOR [32] and Hamama [45], which indicated that the raw milk acidity was generally between 15 and 18 °D for fresh milk. However, the ionic acidity (pH) obtained in all regions was ranged from 6.7 to 6.78. In general, our findings for acidity and pH with those suggested by the French standard for the Dornic acidity of raw milk, representing a pH between 6.6 and 6.8 for cow's milk [46]. When criteria of physical quality in Morocco is considered, our findings for these parameters are generally similar to those previously described by Labioui *et al.* [30] in Mnasra region in West-North. However, our findings are higher than those described by Srairi *et al.* [1] in Rabat-Sale region especially for densities (minimum: 1.0279, maximum: 1.0290) and lesser than those obtained for temperature (minimum: 8.8°C, maximum: 29.1°C). The dispersion of the values found for chemical and physical criteria among samples in these investigated regions could be explicated by the influence of a diversity of factors such the age and health status of the cows, their stage of lactation, environmental conditions and herd management practices. When milk composition quality in Morocco is compared with that described in some regions in Algeria. Our results for total solids and for fat contents remain higher respectively with what was announced by Benlahcen *et al.* [47] in areas of Gdyl, Fleurus, Messerghine and Sidi Bachir in Oran region (24.5, 22.6, 28.3 and 31.3 g/l respectively for fat and 100, 92, 96 and 118 g/l respectively for dry extract). Conversely, our result revealed low values of acidity in comparison to those described by Benlahcen *et al.* [47] (with a minimum of 17 and a maximum of 20 D°) while our findings obtained for pH and density are generally in concordance with those obtained in different areas of Oran (a maximum of 6.7 for pH and a maximum of 1.032 for density) [47]. On the other hand and compared to other studies in Algeria, precisely in Mitidja area (located in Algeria city region), our findings concerning total solids, solids no-fat, protein, fat and density remain higher than what

also described in Mitidja in Algeria region (around of 118 g/l, 87 g/l, 29.1 g/l, 31 g/l and 1.03 were reported respectively for dry matter, defatted dry matter, protein, fat and density) [48]. Taken at whole, these findings show the existence of significant difference between Moroccan and Algerian milk characteristics. Adding to that, our results for fat content, total solids content, acidity and density stay also higher to values described by Gargouri *et al.* [22] in Tunisian dairy herds (30.2 g/l for fat content, 10.82% for total solids, 1.029 for density and 20, 75 D° for acidity). This difference could be associated to the followed farming system and influence of conditions adopted for cow breeding between the three Maghrebian countries in North of Africa.

In the dairy industry, the test of alcohol is normally developed as a simple and rapid indicator of milk freshness. All milk samples tested in this study were normal at 74%. The alcohol test is also considered a practical way of propensity determination of milk for heat coagulation. The other importance of this test that is permitted the detection of abnormal milk, such as milk from animals in late lactation, colostrum, milk from animals suffering from mastitis and milk in which mineral balance has been disturbed according to Gargouri *et al.* [49].

Milk, by its composition and by the different routes that it can undergo before its use either by the dairy industry or by the consumer, constitutes a vector of transmission of microbes, which are usually opportunistic and sometimes dangerous or even pathogenic. The results found by enumeration of different microbial flora of raw cow milk samples in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions are cited in Table 1. The analysis of the microbiological findings obtained for all the regions inspected in this study showed that the majority of milk cow samples examined were contaminated but at different levels. Indeed, the account of Fecal and Total Coliforms indicated an average values of 2.2×10^5 , 2.3×10^5 , 1.1×10^5 and 2.6×10^6 UFC/ml and 3.2×10^5 , 3.1×10^5 , 8.1×10^5 and 3.8×10^5 UFC/ml, respectively; while the *Pseudomonas* spp. enumeration presented values corresponding to 2.7×10^6 , 4.7×10^6 , 1.6×10^7 and 1.3×10^7 UFC/ml, recorded respectively in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions. In addition, the level of total aerobic flora indicated about 9.5×10^6 , 1.7×10^7 , 1.8×10^7 and 2.4×10^7 UFC/ml, respectively in these mentioned above regions. These results reveal strong microbial contamination of the cow milk samples considered.

The total bacteria count was more important in Souk-sebt, Oued-zem and Khouribga regions compared to Fkih-ben-salh region analyzed in this study. According to Ismaili *et al.* [50], this could be related to non-compliance with hygienic conditions and rules during production and milking in addition to lack of refrigeration during milk storage and transportation to the processing industrial unit [50]. When the comparison of loads amount of bacteria obtained in this study with some other areas close to these studied regions is taken into consideration. For example, our findings remain higher than those showed by Ferdous *et al.* [14] in Beni mellal areas (Fecal Coliforms: 10^4 to 10^5 ; Total Coliforms: 7.3×10^4 to 6.49×10^5 and Total Aerobic Flora: 10^5 to 5×10^6 UFC/ml). Indeed, our findings in these regions show that there are noticeable variations as regards the microbial charge. This heterogeneity is well reflected when season is concerned. For example, during March to June; Afif *et al.* [10,11] indicated previously in the same Beni Mellal region a load amount ranged from 0.1×10^5 to 3.2×10^5 , 0.4×10^3 to 4.6×10^3 and 1.1×10^6 to 11.4×10^6 UFC/ml for Total Coliforms, Fecal Coliforms and Total Aerobic Flora; respectively. These findings stay lesser than those described in this study indicating that this difference in charge could be due to non-respect of hygiene conditions and/or poor farm management practices.

In order to avoid biological contamination, several efforts have been made but the effort still to be more pronounced. The highest microbiological charges present in some regions are certainly due to an especially in pre-milking milk handlers and udder preparation, and also when storage equipment and transportation processes to the collect point by individual farms processes [11,17,51,52]. This was confirmed by our observations made for some collecting points in all studied regions. Based on observations made during the collection of samples, we therefore report that improper hygiene and poor farm management practices contributed to the presence of these isolated bacteria in the milk. In these studied regions, milk was obtained from animals by washing their hands and/or the utensils and containers used. In certain cases, untreated groundwater was utilized to wash the containers that were applied for milking. Improving the hygienic conditions of the milking environment and/or utensils may reduce the prevalence of enteropathogenic bacteria. This could be confirmed by the presence of thermoresistant bacteria even at low levels but this indicative of high original bacterial load.

In general, the results of this study corroborate also a number of previous analyses presented in other regions in Morocco characterized with high levels of coliforms existent in raw milk [53]. In this context, a moderate lesser load amount of Total Coliforms, Fecal Coliforms and Total Aerobic Flora (2×10^4 , 5.2×10^3 , 7.4×10^6 UFC/ml) was respectively described in the Mnasra region in Morocco [30] when compared to that encountered in this study. In Rabat-Sale region, Srairi *et al.* [1] showed also a moderate lesser load amount especially for Total Aerobic Flora (1.2×10^7 UFC/ml). However, the levels of Fecal, Total Coliforms and Total Aerobic Flora in all the regions analyzed in this study remain less than reports previously described by Ounine *et al.* [9] in Gharb region (1.07×10^7 , 1.99×10^7 and 1.23×10^8 UFC/ml, respectively). This increase in milk load reflects also problems in the procedures used during milking and those associated to cleaning equipment which appear to be inadequate [54,55].

Regarding the remaining pathogenic group bacteria investigated in this study such as *S. aureus*, *L. monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp. and Clostridium, these bacteria were considered to constitute the main dangerous pathogens to humans. In general, our raw milk samples show a total absence of *S. aureus*, *L. monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp. and Clostridium in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Khouribga, Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions. Our negative findings for *L. monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp. and Clostridium are similar to previous findings reported for Beni Mellal region [10,14] and in other Moroccan regions [56,57]. Concerning the average value of *S. aureus*, another dangerous pathogen, it corresponds to 4.2, 32.0, 56.0 and 80.0 $\times 10^2$ UFC/ml recorded respectively in Fkih-Ben-Salah, Souk-sebt, Khouribga and Oued-zem. These values are more lesser than values described previously by Ferdous *et al.* [14,15] ($>10^3$ UCF/ml) and Afif *et al.* [10,11] (0.8 to 5×10^3 UCF/ml) in Beni Mellal region and in Tadla plain, respectively. Also, our results indicate low loads compared to other Moroccan regions especially in the Gharb regions (9×10^4 UCF/ml; 5×10^5 UCF/ml) [57], and in the Rabat region (25×10^5 UCF/ml); Hamama [45] indicating that several efforts have been made to decrease threshold of the milk *S. aureus* load and by consequent enhancing the quality of hygienic milk in Beni Mellal region. Relating to Maghreb countries, our results reveal also differences with reports in Algeria and Tunisia regions, principally in case of *S. aureus* and Clostridium prevalence that was in the range of 24.71% and 2.87% respectively in Tizi Ouzou region [58]. Also, in Oran region (Algeria west), a charge of 8.4×10^5 , 72.3×10^5 ,

19.4×10^5 and 9.8×10^4 UFC/ml was described in Sidi Bachir area for Fecal coliforms, Total Aerobic Flora, *S. aureus* and *C. perfringens*, respectively; whereas a level load of 27.1×10^2 , 3.6×10^4 , 2.7×10^4 and 0 UFC/ml was reported in Gdyl area for the same germs. In addition, a level of 38×10^4 was observed in case of Messerghine region and a load of 2.1×10^2 UFC/ml was described in Fleurus region [47]. Finally; in Boumerdes region in Algeria, Kaouche *et al.* [59] indicated an important difference in the profiles of several studied microbial pathogens showing the presence of a deterioration in the microbiological quality of raw milk (*S. aureus*: 23%, Sulphite-reducing *Clostridia*: 30%, Listeria: 13%). *S. aureus*, is a bacteria that is easily transmitted from one cow to another, is frequently responsible for causing subclinical mastitis. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that the teat cups must be rinsed and disinfected after milking an infected cow. It is also advisable to spray the teats after milking with a certified soaking solution.

The analysis and interpretation of somatic milk cell counts (SMCC) is considered as an important and essential step in the epidemiological interpretation of a mammary infection problem in a herd [60,61]. Thus, SMCC analysis is a good way to assess the general health status of the udder [62,63]. In Morocco, data available on SMCC are few; the average values observed of SMCC in this study are 344 400, 284 200, 323 900 and 331 800 cells/ml in Fkih-ben-salh, Souk-sebt, Khouribga and Oued-zem regions, respectively. These values are in concordance with what announced by standards for SMCC ($< \text{or} = 400\,000$ cells/ml) [64].

The cellular values recorded in these considered interior regions of the kingdom are high compared to the average (232 000 cells/ml) found during the study carried out in a sub-humid region of Tunisia by Bouraoui *et al.* [65]. This difference could be explained mainly by the study environment (semi-arid vs. sub-humid), the size of the herds monitored (Small vs Large) and the farming system adopted (Hors sol vs forage and pastoral availability) [66].

Numerous factors could be responsible agents for the evolution of SMCC such as breed, rank and stage of lactation, month and season of calving, individual milk production [62,66-68] and the infectious status of udders [61,69]. Infected cows showed simply an increasing in milk cell counts. Adding to that several factors cited and that influence the SMCC. Nevertheless, infections caused by Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CNS) (the most common) or by major pathogens (mainly *S. aureus*) are the major cause of increased SMCC.

Inter-relations between chemical, physical and hygienic parameters

The most significant interactions between the different parameters carried out in this study are cited in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Significant correlations between chemical and physical parameters in raw milk.

As observed, the fat content of milk was strong positively correlated with solids no fat, brix and pH and strong negatively correlated with acidity. However, acidity was strong positively correlated with temperature. In addition, the protein content was strong positively correlated with solids no fat and brix and strong negatively correlated with density. The solids no fat was also strong positively correlated with fat content, protein content, brix and density. These positive correlations reflected that any decreasing or increasing in solids no fat rate will be influenced by any change in any rate of other compositions of milk such as protein content, brix, fat content and density of milk. For example, acidity was strong positively correlated with temperature. Temperature plays a key role in the degradation of the raw milk quality because it promotes the rapid development of the milk microbial flora that transforms lactose mainly in lactic acid designated by developed acidity, thus accelerating its instability; thereafter, the deterioration of its quality [70]. For example, at high temperatures, tricalcium phosphate can precipitate and cause an

increase in acidity triggered by dissociation of phosphate [70]. However, acidity was strong negatively associated with fat content and pH as previously reported by Gargouri *et al.* [49], especially for the correlation between acidity and fat content. Statistical analysis in our study showed also that of density was strong positively correlated with protein content, solids no fat and brix, in opposition to other studies that showed a positive correlation between density and total solids and a negative correlation between density and fat content [49,70]. Furthermore, brix was strong positively correlated with fat content, protein content, solids no fat and density. It appears that positive correlation observed between density and brix is a normal case, taking example of milk wetting that causes a decrease in its density [42] and also in its brix and in all chemical and physical parameters. For this, the strong positive correlation observed between brix and other parameters such as fat content, protein content, solids no fat and density on the one hand and the strong positive correlation found between solids no fat, fat content and protein content, brix and density on the other hand could be considered as the important correlations observed between one and four parameters in this study. In addition, pH was positively correlated with fat content and strong negatively correlated with acidity and temperature. Finally, there are no significant correlation observed between total solids and all parameters studied of raw milk in this study.

Inter-relations between hygienic criteria, pathogenic bacteria and SCCM

The correlations analysis between the different parameters carried out in this regards are outlined in Figure 3.

n.s: no signification,

Fig 3. Inter-relations between hygienic criteria, pathogenic bacteria and SCCM.

The total number of total aerobic flora encountered in milk was positively correlated with total coliforms, fecal coliforms and *S. aureus*. However, the total number of SMCC was negatively correlated with total aerobic flora, total coliforms, fecal coliforms and *S. aureus*. This reflects that the total number of SMCC varies in the opposite way of the other parameters studied. In Morocco, measurement of SMCC of milk for diagnosis of subclinical mastitis is considered as a new and relevant technique used by the milk processing units and is not frequently used by farmers. Worldly, the SMCC has been extensively used as an indicator of intramammary gland infections; the SMCC is included as an important component of the definition of mastitis disease in dairy herds, as the milk SMCC evidently increases during bacterial infections of mammary gland as previously described by several studies [72-74]. According to Hogan *et al.* [49], the SMCC level of bacteriological findings differs between bacteria species. Thus, somatic cells are, in great quantity, cells of the immune system (80% in uninfected quarters, and 99% in quarters with mastitis)

[76]. The average values observed of SMCC in this study are 344 400, 284 200, 323 900 and 331 800 cells/ml in Fkih-ben-salh, Souk-sebt, Khouribga and Oued-zem regions, respectively. These values are in concordance with what announced by standards for SMCC ($<$ or $=$ 400 000 cells/ml) [64]. Consequently, these findings remain normal because of mammary gland cell renewal cycle. According to Sharma *et al.* [22], the glands epithelial cells are normally shed and get renewed; however, during infection the numbers increase. In addition, all milk samples tested for the detection of chemical residues of the antibiotics were negatives. When all these results are taken into consideration, we can conclude that the cows are normally healthy. The no signification observed between SMCC and other parameters could be explained by several sanitary, environmental and technical factors. For example, hygienic criteria such as faecal and total coliforms and total aerobic flora are external factors that reflect the conditions in which the milking was carried out while SMCC reflect internal health status of the mammary gland. In addition, the absence of pathogenic bacteria and the low level observed for *S. aureus* supporting this assumption. In the literature, Gargouri *et al.* [49] showed a high association between *S. aureus* and SMCC and the majority of the other hygienic criteria contrary to what we found in this study. This difference could be associated to high level that they showed especially for SMCC and also for *S. aureus* in comparison to our findings that remain in concordance with what announced by standards for SMCC ($<$ or $=$ 400 000 cells/ml) [64]. However, Gargouri *et al.* [49] showed that according to this relation, *S. aureus* was responsible for 53% of cases of mastitis in dairy cows. Furthermore, various studies reported that intra-mammary infection caused by *S. aureus* usually results in an increased SMCC [77-79]. Worldly, the SMCC has been widely used as an indicator of intramammary gland infections; the MSCC is included as an important component of the definition of mastitis disease in dairy herds, as the milk MSCC evidently increases during bacterial infections of mammary gland, as was previously reported [72-74]. Finally, the association analysis between the total number of fecal coliforms and total coliforms and between fecal coliforms and *S. aureus* on the one hand, and between the total number of total coliforms and SMCC was not statistically relevant on the other hand. Accordingly, any increasing/decreasing in total number of each parameter conduct directly to variation in other parameter proportionally.

It appears that SMCC, pathogenic bacteria and research of chemical residues of antibiotics in the raw milk are the most promising parameters could be utilized by the milk processing industry for monitoring milk from cows suffering subclinical mastitis. On the other hand, hygienic criteria such as total coliforms, fecal coliforms and total aerobic flora level retained during milking was also higher and exceeding the normal threshold, reinforcing this hypothesis that most of these herds were confronted with hygienic problems during milking. In conclusion, the milk processing industry and milk producers can use several simple and rapid tools to evaluate the overall quality of milk, especially hygienic quality and those which indicate the health status of the herd.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study showed a notable variation in chemical and physical criteria. Of note, protein rate stays higher in case of Oued-zem region than what was observed in other studied regions, this could be related to local adopting cow in this region, especially the brown Atlas cow. Analysis of the microbiological findings found, for all the regions investigated in this study, revealed that the great majority of milk cow samples studied were contaminated but at diverse levels exceeding in many times the normal threshold, supporting the hypothesis that all these herds were confronted with problems in milking hygiene associated to the conditions of raw milk handling practices during milking, storage and transportation especially in Souk-sebt and Oued-zem regions. All milk samples were negatives for the major pathogen bacteria and for the detection of chemical residues of the antibiotics. The somatic milk cell counts are in concordance with what announced by standards. These findings can inform the milk producers on the sanitary status of udder health on the one hand and the processing units on the milk quality on the one other hand. Statistical analysis showed a significant inter-relationship between several parameters carried out in this study, especially between physico-chemical parameters on the one hand and between hygienic criteria on the one other hand. Finally, the milk producers are required to deploy additional efforts to improve hygienic conditions during and after milking in order to reduce bacterial load. In conclusion, this study shows several simple and rapid tools that can be used by milk producers and the processing industry to assess the overall quality of milk, including hygienic and physicochemical quality.

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